

Definition of the Correspondence and Epistolary Research (CER) Ontology

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1 Introduction

The following document describes the Correspondence and Epistolary Research (CER) Ontology. This ontology provides a comprehensive semantic model for the domain of historical letters within the context of academic research. It captures the semantic aspects of correspondence, including metadata related to correspondence actions, index data referring to entities mentioned within the letter text, and the semantic content of the letters themselves. Additionally, the ontology encompasses the annotation and study of letters as research objects, particularly within the framework of an editing process.

In developing the ontology, we adopt the concept of a 'semantic scholarly digital edition' as outlined by Spadini and Tomasi (Spadini & Tomasi, 2021). This approach addresses the need for formal models that accommodate multiple perspectives on textual objects and underscore the data-centric approach of scholarly editing.

The CER Ontology is being developed as part of the '[Correspondences of Early Romanticism](#)' project. It uses the CIDOC CRM in its Version 7.1.2 (Bekiari et al., 2022) as a foundational ontology and references the Basic Formal Ontology (BFO) (Arp et al., 2015) as well as the correspDesc-element of the TEI Guidelines (Stadler et al., 2016). Accordingly, this document's form and structure are loosely based on the format introduced by the definitions of the CRM and its compatible model.

1.1 Scope

This text defines the model of correspondence-based communication processes within the epistolary knowledge transfer of the 'Romantics' among themselves and with other correspondents in the period of Early Romanticism (1790–1802). It is developed as a domain ontology in the context of the project "Correspondences of the Early Romanticism" (CER) and uses the CIDOC CRM (ISO21127) as a foundational reference ontology.

The CER-ontology has been developed within an iterative process in a middle-out approach (Noy & McGuinness, 2001): First, the most specific classes of the knowledge domain were identified based on already existing data from the "[Digital Edition of the Correspondence of August Wilhelm Schlegel \(KAWS\)](#)" as well as on communication with the domain experts. Then, classes of the CIDOC CRM were used to define the overlying, more general concepts and thereby establish an overarching and broader conceptual framework. In doing so, the domain-specific concepts not only are compatible with other models using the CIDOC CRM, but also ensure interoperability with ontologies within the (Digital) Humanities domain, and allow the CER ontology in its OWL-serialisation to draw on the semantics and inheritance hierarchies of the CRM. Also, the CIDOC CRM superclasses function as a communication medium, enabling a clear understanding of the concepts of the CER-ontology for researchers familiar with the CIDOC CRM.

Furthermore, the CER-ontology follows the design principles of modular ontology modelling (Shimizu et al., 2023), meaning that the ontology's classes are grouped in small self-contained modules. These modules are interlinked between each other but may be reused separately, depending on the research question. At this moment, the following modules have been identified to be of interest and to fall within the ontology's scope:

- 1) [Global](#)
- 2) [Letter](#)

- 3) [Correspondence Action](#)
- 4) [Independent Continuant](#)
- 5) [Specifically Dependent Continuant](#)
- 6) [Statement](#)
- 7) [Biographical Information](#)
- 8) [Co-Presence](#)
- 9) [Editing](#)

The ontology's scope is based on competency questions relevant to the aims of the project such as:

- Which persons correspond with each other and over what timeframe?
- Which letters mention specific works, institutions, periodicals, individuals, or locations, and in what context?
- Are there consistent patterns in how certain works, institutions, periodicals, individuals, or locations are mentioned within the statements?
- Is there a variation in how index data, such as works, institutions, periodicals, or individuals, is referenced based on the correspondents involved (for example if a work is reviewed positively or negatively)?
- Do some persons consistently appear in the letters of others, even if they never had direct contact through correspondence?
- Is there a tendency for certain index information, such as works, institutions, periodicals, individuals, or locations, to be frequently mentioned together?
- Do researchers edit the content of the letters in distinct ways?
- Do persons who exchange letters from the same location tend to discuss similar works, institutions, periodicals, or individuals in their correspondence?

The CER ontology's primary purpose is to answer these or similar questions. In doing so, it aims to represent the knowledge domain of the romantic circle and its contemporary everyday life around 1800 as presented in the correspondences, as well as the editing process of these letters. This representation facilitates research into the epistolary communication processes, the history of ideas and social history as well as the epistolary knowledge transfer of the 'Romantics' among themselves and with other correspondents. Therefore, the ontology's scope is to systematically explore the group's formation and dynamics, as well as the associated transfer of knowledge, and to focus on a form of communication that largely determined contemporary everyday life. Additionally, it will also open up a new paradigm for the study of letters and expand scholarly reflection on the theory and social practice of 'Geselligkeit' in early Romanticism and on the role and function of the letter in this context.

The primary user group of the CER-ontology are the researchers working in the project "Correspondences of the Early Romanticism". Its principal function as a domain ontology is therefore to answer the project's research questions concerning communications processes and the ensuing knowledge transfer. However, because of the model's module structure, together with its references to the CIDOC CRM, it attains generic characteristics, and may be used as a model for other research projects as well. This covers similar data, like communication sources, such as historical letter data, but is not limited to this case. It also includes research questions that emphasise the dynamic relation among participants in knowledge transfer within these communication contexts, unravelling the underlying social structures and gatherings.

1.2 Status

The model presented in this document has so far been validated in the project “Correspondences of the Early Romanticism”, funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG). This document describes a consolidated version developed from the experiences of the researchers in the project, with the aim to present it for review and further adoption to the widest possible community. The model is not “finished”. It rather represents a version-controlled status quo of the recent progress (October 2025) and will be developed further.

1.3 Naming Conventions

All the classes declared were given both a name and an identifier constructed according to the conventions used in the CIDOC CRM model. For classes that identifier consists of the abbreviation CER (for **C**orrespondences of the **E**arly **R**omanticism) followed by a number. Resulting properties were also given a name and an identifier, constructed according to the same conventions. That identifier consists of the abbreviation CERP (**C**orrespondences of the **E**arly **R**omanticism **P**roperties) followed by a number. They correspond to letters “E” and “P”, respectively, in the CIDOC CRM naming conventions.

In the OWL implementation, the “CER”-prefix corresponds to the RDF-prefix “cer:”, meaning that a class such as “CER1 Letter” is expressed as “cer:1_Letter”, and a property such as “CERP1 is identified by” as “cer:P1_is_identified_by”.

Whenever CIDOC CRM classes are used in the model, the name given in the CIDOC CRM itself is used.

2 Class and Property Hierarchies

Class and Property Hierarchies follow the format as established in the definition of the CIDOC CRM (Bekiari et al., 2022). They contain the classes and properties of the CER ontology as well as relevant (super-)classes of the CIDOC CRM.

2.1 Class Hierarchy

Classes and Properties are sorted hierarchically and alphabetically. Classes of the CER Ontology are underlined, classes with the prefix “E” are references to the CIDOC CRM.

E1 CRM Entity
E54 – Dimension
CER26 – – Start-Date
CER27 – – End-Date
E77 – Persistent Item
E39 – – Actor
E74 – – – Group
CER7 – – – – Institution
E21 – – – Person
CER17 – – – – Person
E70 – – Thing
E71 – – – Human-Made-Thing
E28 – – – – Conceptual Object
CER5 – – – – – Periodical
E90 – – – – – Symbolic Object
E41 – – – – – Appellation
E42 – – – – – Identifier
CER21 – – – – – Identifier
E73 – – – – – Information Object
E31 – – – – – Document
E32 – – – – – Authority Document
CER16 – – – – – Authority Document
CER2 – – – – – Reference Dataset
E33 – – – – – Linguistic Object
CER4 – – – – – Index Information
CER3 – – – – – Lettertext
E55 – – – – – Type
CER23 – – – – – Assigned Gender
CER25 – – – – – Confidence Value
CER9 – – – – – Illocution
E56 – – – – – Language
CER20 – – – – – Language
CER10 – – – – – Proposition
CER11 – – – – – Theme
CER6 – – – – – Work
E24 – – – – – Physical Human-Made Thing
E22 – – – – – Human-Made Object

CER1 – – – – – Letter
 E53 – Place
CER19 – – Place
 E2 – Temporal Entity
 E4 – – Period
 E5 – – – Event
 E7 – – – – Activity
 E13 – – – – – Attribute Assignment
CER22 – – – – – Gender Assignment
CER8 – – – – – Statement
CER12 – – – – – Correspondence Action
CER14 – – – – – Receiving
CER13 – – – – – Sending
 E65 – – – – – Creation
CER15 – – – – – Editing
CER24 – – – – Co-Presence

2.2 Property Hierarchy

Property	Property Name	Entity – Domain	Entity – Range
CERP1	is identified by	E1 Entity	CER21 Identifier
CERP2	has language (is language of)	CER3 Lettertext	CER20 Language
CERP3	carries (is carried by)	CER1 Letter	CER3 Lettertext
CERP4	has generic theme (is generic theme of)	CER3 Lettertext	CER11 Theme
CERP5	has component (is component of)	CER3 Lettertext	CER4 Index Information
CERP6	has time-span (is time-span of)	CER12 Correspondence Action CER15 Editing CER24 Co-Presence	CER18 Time-Span
CERP7	took place at (witnessed)	CER12 Correspondence Action CER24 Co-Presence	CER19 Place
CERP8	carried out by (performed)	CER12 Correspondence Action CER15 Editing CER22 Gender Assignment	CER7 Institution CER17 Person

CERP9	was intended use of (was made for)	CER12 Correspondence Action	CER1 Letter
CERP10	lists (is listed in)	CER16 Authority Record	CER4 Index Information
CERP11	implied in (implies)	CER8 Statement	CER3 Lettertext
CERP12	is about (is subject of)	CER4 Index Information	CER5 Periodical CER6 Work CER7 Institution CER17 Person CER19 Place
CERP13	has subject (is subject of)	CER8 Statement	CER4 Index Information
CERP14	has object (is object of)	CER8 Statement	CER4 Index Information
CERP15	has illocution (is illocution of)	CER8 Statement	CER9 Illocution
CERP16	has proposition (is proposition of)	CER8 Statement	CER10 Proposition
CERP17	documents (is documented in)	CER2 Reference Data Set	CER3 Lettertext CER1 Letter
CERP20	– infers (is inferred from)	CER2 Reference Data Set	CER24 Co-Presence
CERP18	has created (was created by)	CER15 Editing	CER2 Reference Data Set
CERP19	had duration (was duration of)	CER18 Time-Span	CER26 Start Date CER27 End Date
CERP21	assigned gender attribute to (gender was attributed by)	CER22 Gender Assignment	CER17 Person
CERP22	assigned gender property of type (is type of gender property assigned)	CER22 Gender Assignment	CER23 Assigned Gender
CERP23	had participant	CER24 Co-Presence	CER17 Person

3 CER Ontology Class Declarations

Classes are organised in modules of related content. These modules are situated either in the “real world”, which indicates entities that have existed as physical objects or conceptual objects, or in the “letter world”, which encompasses all contents of a letter and its semantic meaning. The “Letter”-module’s classes describe assertions which are either made by the writers or which are interpretations made by the editors of the letters. Therefore, the module “Editing” is a part of the “letter world” as well.

Classes that are relevant for more than one module (e.g. CER19 Place, or CER1 Letter) are described in detail when they are first mentioned. Otherwise, the class is only listed in the module description.

All examples detailing the classes and properties are taken directly from the project data and are therefore in German. The declarations follow the format as established in the definition of the CIDOC CRM.

Module “Global”

This module describes classes that can have a connection to instances of several or all other classes. The module “Global” includes the following classes:

- CER18 Time-Span
- CER19 Place
- CER21 Identifier
- CER26 Start Date
- CER27 End Date

CER18 Time-Span

Subclass of:
E52 Time-Span

Scope Note:

This class refers to the time-span in which an event or an activity took place. In the CER data, this corresponds mainly to correspondence actions (CER12 Correspondence Action), and editing processes (CER15 Editing), but also to other events such as CER24 Co-Presence.

Instances of this class can also contain uncertain or editorially inferred dates. Computable values of certain dates are given via the classes CER26 Start Date and CER27 End Date.

Examples:

- 07.03.1798
- 2019-11-11
- [Anfang Dezember 1797] (beginning of december 1797)

In First Order Logic:

$CER18(x) \Rightarrow E52(x)$

Properties:

CERP19 had duration (was duration of): CER26 Start Date
CER27 End Date

CER19 Place

Subclass of:

E53 Place

Scope Note:

This class is used to refer to places which are involved in an event or activity such as a Correspondence Action (CER12 Correspondence Action), and to places which are mentioned in a letter text (CER4 Index Information). They may be identified via authority records such as geo names (CER16 Authority Record) but this is not mandatory. Places are not used to give more information about the provenance of a letter, as this is not within the ontology's scope.

Examples:

- Weimar
- Schloss Laufen (Laufen-Uhwiesen)

In First Order Logic:

$CER19(x) \Rightarrow E53(x)$

CER21 Identifier

SubClass Of:

E42 Identifier

Scope Note:

The class CER21 Identifier comprises unique codes in the form of numbers and letters assigned to instances of all classes in order to identify them uniquely and permanently.

Examples:

- 2911
- 6213
- AWS-aw-000j

In First Order Logic:

$CER21(x) \Rightarrow E42(x)$

CER26 Start Date

SubClass Of:

E54 Dimension

Scope Note:

This class represents the beginning of a CER18 Time-Span, expressed in computable values in ISO-format.

Examples:

- 2019-11-11

In First Order Logic:

$CER26(x) \Rightarrow E54(x)$

CER27 End Date

SubClass Of:

E54 Dimension

Scope Note:

This class represents the end of a CER18 Time-Span, expressed in computable values in ISO-format.

Examples:

- 2019-11-11

In First Order Logic:

$CER27(x) \Rightarrow E54(x)$

Module “Letter”

This module describes the letter itself as a physical expression as well as its textual representation, the letter's content. By separating the letter's materiality from its semantic contents, this module might be extended in the future with classes describing contents attached to a letter. This might contain things like drawings, texts other than the letter text itself, etc., depending on the source material.

The module “Letter” includes the following classes:

- CER1 Letter
- CER3 Lettertext
- CER20 Language

CER1 Letter

Subclass of:

E22 Human-Made Object

Scope Note:

This class encompasses the physical expression of a letter, namely the original manuscript as a communication object. It encompasses various information, such as the textual content of the

letter. Its primary function was to facilitate the exchange of textual messages between two or more individuals.

Examples:

- The letter sent on 24 June 1798, by August Wilhelm von Schlegel from Göttingen to Christian Gottlob Heyne in Dresden that is archived in the Saxon State and University Library Dresden
- The letter sent on 19 November 1791, by August Wilhelm von Schlegel from Amsterdam to Gottfried August Bürger in Göttingen that is printed in Strodtmann, Adolf: "Briefe von und an Gottfried August Bürger. Ein Beitrag zur Literaturgeschichte seiner Zeit. Aus dem Nachlasse Bürger's und anderen, meist handschriftlichen Quellen. Bd. 4. Berlin 1874, S. 137–139".

In First Order Logic:

$CER1(x) \Rightarrow E22(x)$

Properties:

CERP3 carries (is carried by): CER3 Lettext

CER3 Lettext

Subclass of:

E33 Linguistic Object

Scope Note:

This class comprises the textual representation of a letter, specifically focusing on its semantic, written content. It does not address the material aspects of the letter, meaning that the origin of the text (whether from the original manuscript or a printed version) is not considered.¹

In this project, the texts are transcribed and edited in adherence to the [guidelines of the Digital Edition of the Correspondence of August Wilhelm Schlegel \(KAWS\)](#). Following these guidelines, the texts are in diplomatic transcription.

Examples:

- Weimar den 12. April [1798] Werthester Freund, Ich habe sogleich ihren Auftrag wegen der Comödienbillets ausgerichtet, und Sie können deßhalb unbesorgt seyn. Wie ich höre kostet das Stück 16 Groschen. Wieland kömt auch herüber, und so unlieb mir dieß wegen der Collision ist, so angenehm, hoff' ich soll es für Sie seyn; denn in einer größern Gesellschaft würden Sie ihn doch nur wenig genießen. – – Nur in einem freundschaftlichen Kreise ist er liebenswürdig. – – Von ihrer Uebersetzung spricht er mit vieler Wärme und Achtung. Sie liefern uns doch noch zu Ostern einen Band? Ich kann es kaum erwarten, so freue ich mich auf diesen Genuß. Wieland hat mir aufgetragen ihm den Schillerschen M.[usen] A.[lmanach] von diesem Jahre nach Osm.[annstedt] zu schicken. Er ist nicht abgeneigt ihn, so wie die Dorothea, diesen Sommer zu recensiren. Wie ich höre verreisen Sie wirklich. Ich beneide Sie. Ich darf wegen überhäufte Arbeiten daran nicht ein Mahl denken. – – Eben deßhalb muß ich schließen. Leben Sie wohl,

¹ The representation of textual materiality respectively the study and edition of (ancient) handwritten texts finds its coverage within the CRMTex model, which is a compatible model of the CIDOC CRM. However, within the CER-Ontology knowledge domain, the materiality of the letters is not (yet) a focus of research. Instead, the ontology focuses on the contents and semantics of the texts of the letters. This decision is based on our priority to delving into the semantics of a letter text rather than its materiality.

liebster Schlegel, ich umarme Sie in Gedanken und bin unabänderlich Ihr F. P. S. Haben Sie doch die Gefälligkeit diese von Berlin aus mir abgedrungene Antwort in das nächste Stück der Litteratur Zeitung zu fördern. Nach dem Abdruck, und wenn ich weiß, wie viel Zeilen es ausmacht, will ich mich darüber mit Ihnen abfinden. Ich bin so noch von Alters her in ihrer Schuld. – Die freundschaftlichsten Empfehlungen von meiner Caroline an die Ihrige, und von mir an HH. Professor Hufeland und Schütz und HE. Tischbein.

In First Order Logic:

$CER3(x) \Rightarrow E33(x)$

Properties:

CERP2 has language (is language of): CER20 Language

CERP4 has generic theme (is generic theme of): CER11 Theme

CERP5 has component (is component of): CER4 Index Information

CER20 Language

SubClass Of:

E56 Language

Scope Note:

This class defines the language in which the letter text (CER3 Lettertext) of a letter from the romantic circle is written. A letter text may have more than one language.

Examples:

- Deutsch, Englisch
- Französisch

In First Order Logic:

$CER20(x) \Rightarrow E56(x)$

Module “Correspondence Action”

This module is adapted from the TEI standard for correspondence “<correspAction>” which contains “a structured description of the place, the name of a person/organization and the date related to the sending/receiving of a message or any other action related to the correspondence”. (Stadler et al., 2016) While in the CER-ontology, it describes the exchange of letters, in other contexts, it might as well be used to represent further structures of written or oral communication exchange.

The module “Correspondence Actions” includes the following classes:

- *CER1 Letter*
- CER12 Correspondence Action
- CER13 Sending
- CER14 Receiving
- *CER17 Person (described in Module “Independent Continuant”)*
- *CER18 Time-Span*

- CER19 Place

CER12 Correspondence Action

Subclass of:

E7 Activity

Superclass of:

CER13 Sending

CER14 Receiving

Scope Note:

This class comprises the activities making up processes of correspondence items involving at least two persons. This class and its subclasses have been adapted from the [TEI standard for correspondences](#), specifically drawing from the [correspAction-element](#). The aim of this class is to refine categorization in order to illuminate the multifaceted layers inherent in the transmission of written communication.

Even though the correspAction element covers the sending, receiving, transmitting, redirecting and forwarding correspondence items, due to the scope of the project, the Version 2.0 of the CER-ontology presently encompasses solely the sending and receiving actions. If needed, additional classes can easily be added by other projects. This decision is due to the fact that the current database contains annotations only for the sending and receiving actions, which are consequently the only ones within our current scope of the knowledge domain.

Examples:

- The act of sending a letter was conducted by August Wilhelm von Schlegel in Jena on 7 March 1798.
- The act of receiving the same letter which was conducted by Johann Joachim Eschenburg in Braunschweig.
- The letter sent by Friedrich Schlegel and Friedrich Schleiermacher in Berlin on 15 Jan 1798 which was received by August Wilhelm von Schlegel in Jena.

In First Order Logic:

$CER12(x) \Rightarrow E7(x)$

Properties:

CERP9 was intended use of (was made for): CER1 Letter

CERP8 carried out by (performed): CER17 Person

CERP6 has time-span (is time-span of): CER18 Time-Span

CERP7 took place at (witnessed): CER19 Place

CER13 Sending

Subclass of:

CER12 Correspondence Action

Scope Note:

This class comprises the sending process of correspondence items involving at least two persons. It has been adapted from the TEI standard for correspondences, specifically drawing from the `correspAction` element. The aim of this class is to supply information concerning the sending or dispatch of a message.

Examples:

- The sending of a letter by August Wilhelm von Schlegel in Jena on 7 March 1798.
- The sending of a letter by Friedrich Schlegel and Friedrich Schleiermacher in Berlin on 15 January 1798.

In First Order Logic:

$CER13(x) \Rightarrow CER12(x)$

CER14 Receiving

Subclass of:

CER12 Correspondence Action

Scope Note:

This class comprises the receiving process of correspondence items involving at least two persons. It has been adapted from the TEI standard for correspondences, specifically drawing from the `correspAction` element. The aim of this class is to supply information concerning the receipt of a message.

Examples:

- The receiving of a letter by Johann Joachim Eschenburg in Braunschweig on 7 March 1798.
- The receiving of a letter by August Wilhelm von Schlegel in Jena on 15 January 1798.

In First Order Logic:

$CER14(x) \Rightarrow CER12(x)$

Module “Independent Continuant”

In this module, entities are described that correlate with the letters, either through being mentioned in the texts themselves, or by being involved in their sending and receiving.

The term “Independent Continuant” derives from the Basic Formal ontology:

“Continuants are entities that continue to exist through time; they may gain and lose parts (for instance, as an organism gains and loses cells), but at each point in time at which they exist at all they nonetheless exist completely. (...) An independent continuant is a continuant entity that is the bearer of qualities. (...) [Their] identity and existence can be maintained through gain and loss of parts, and also through changes in those qualities, and through gain and loss of dispositions, and of roles.” (Arp et al., 2015)

For example, the person August Wilhelm Schlegel as an independent continuant exists within the context of a letter or the correspondence process, but he also exists independently beyond the letter's context as a person per se.

The module "Independent Continuant" includes the following classes:

- CER5 Periodical
- CER6 Work
- CER7 Institution
- CER16 Authority Record
- CER17 Person
- *CER19 Place*

CER5 Periodical

Subclass of:

E28 Conceptual Object

Scope Note:

This class comprises periodicals that are referenced, mentioned, and discussed within the letters of the early Romantic period.

Examples:

- Göttingische gelehrte Anzeigen
- Jahrbücher der preußischen Monarchie unter der Regierung Friedrich Wilhelms III.

In First Order Logic:

$CER5(x) \Rightarrow E28(x)$

CER6 Work

Subclass of:

E28 Conceptual Object

Scope Note:

This class comprises works that are mentioned, talked about and discussed within the letters of the period of early Romanticism. At this stage of the project, the instances of the class CER6 Work also hold information about the title and author(s) of a certain work. Some of the instances may also contain information translations, receptions e.g. about the work.

Examples:

- Shakespeare, William: Die lustigen Weiber zu Windsor [Ü: Johann Joachim Eschenburg] (Shakespeare, William: The Merry Wives of Windsor, translated by Johann Joachim Eschenburg)
- Dante, Alighieri: Divina commedia
- Schlegel, August Wilhelm von: Herder, Johann Gottfried von: Terpsichore (Rezension) (Schlegel, August Wilhelm von: Herder, Johann Gottfried von: Terpsichore (Review))

In First Order Logic:

$CER6(x) \Rightarrow E28(x)$

CER7 Institution

Subclass of:

E74 Group

Scope Note:

This class comprises historical institutions that are referenced, discussed, and mentioned within the letters of the early Romanticism period, as well as the institutions accountable for managing and curating the data of the letters associated with the research project.

Examples:

- Leipziger Buchmesse
- Erzbergwerk Rammelsberg (Goslar)

In First Order Logic:

$CER7(x) \Rightarrow E74(x)$

CER16 Authority Record

Subclass of:

E32 Authority Document

Scope Note:

This class comprises identification numbers of authority records, such as the [geonames](#) ID of a place or the GND ID ([Integrated Authority File of the German National Library](#)) of a person. Due to the importance of authority records for the semantic web and LO(U)D and their role in uniquely identifying entities across databases, the subclass was created to set these records apart from other authority documents as specified by E32 Authority Document. It serves to enhance the metadata of letters and provides additional information about instances mentioned within the letters. These identification numbers contribute to enriching the contextual details and knowledge associated with the instances.

This class is listed under this module instead of the module “Editing process” as the assignment of authority records to entities constitutes documentations of these entities with external sources. Editing on the other hand describes more of a research process within a project. In the latter case the decisions which led to the annotation of a resource are more likely to be documented and known to the project members. Even though authority records are at best as well documented and were part of a research process, they represent more the result of this process while the editing leading to an annotation of a resource in a letter illustrates more the process itself.

Examples:

- GND: 118607979
- Geoname: 2950159
- VIAF: 22156190

In First Order Logic:

$CER16(x) \Rightarrow E32(x)$

Properties:

CERP10 lists (is listed in): CER4 Index Information

CER17 Person

Subclass of:

E21 Person

Scope Note:

The class CER17 Person refers exclusively to editors and historical persons, as these are the only persons collected in the data.

Examples:

- Schlegel, Dorothea von
- Fath, Laura

In First Order Logic:

$CER17(x) \Rightarrow E21(x)$

Module “Specifically Dependent Continuant”

In this module, entities are described that correlate with the letters, by being mentioned in the texts and edited within an editing process.

The term “Specifically Dependent Continuant” derives from the Basic Formal ontology:

“Continuants are entities that continue to exist through time; they may gain and lose parts (for instance, as an organism gains and loses cells), but at each point in time at which they exist at all they nonetheless exist completely. (...) A specifically dependent continuant is a continuant entity that depends on one or more specific independent continuants for its existence. Dependent continuants exhibit existential dependence in the sense that, in order for a dependent continuant to exist, some other entity in which it inheres (intuitively, an entity enjoying a larger degree of concreteness) must exist also.” (Arp et al., 2015)

For example, the index information, such as the mention of “August Wilhelm Schlegel”, as a specifically dependent continuant exists only within the context of a letter. It is not to be confused with August Wilhelm Schlegel as an independent person but rather as a representation of this person in a letter’s context. Without the letter this representation can not exist.

The module “Specifically Dependent Continuant” includes the following classes:

- CER4 Index Information
- CER11 Theme

CER4 Index Information

Subclass of:

E33 Linguistic Object

Scope Note:

This class comprises index information referring to the semantic representation of historical persons, historical periodicals, historical works, historical institutions and places within the text of a letter. This means that entities of this class represent a textual conceptualization of these historical persons, periodicals, works, institutions, and places, not their physical manifestation, which is expressed in the classes CER17 Person, CER19 Place, CER5 Periodical, CER6 Work and CER7 Institution.

Examples:

- The work "Shakespeare, William: Die lustigen Weiber zu Windsor [Ü: Johann Joachim Eschenburg]" mentioned in the letter sent from August Wilhelm Schlegel in Jena to Johann Joachim Eschenburg in Braunschweig on 3 July 1798.
- The periodical "Göttingische gelehrte Anzeigen" mentioned in the letter sent from Johan F. W. Schlegel in Kopenhagen to August Wilhelm Schlegel in Göttingen on 15 October 1790.
- The person "Schelling, Caroline von" mentioned in the letter sent from August Wilhelm von Schlegel in Berlin to Georg Joachim Göschen in Leipzig on 26 May 1798.

In First Order Logic:

$CER4(x) \Rightarrow E33(x)$

Properties:

CERP12 is about (is subject of): CER5 Periodical
CER6 Work
CER7 Institution
CER17 Person
CER19 Place

CER11 Theme

Subclass of:

E55 Type

Scope Note:

This class comprises general topics or keywords that are implicitly mentioned within the letters of the early Romanticism period. In contrast to the instances of CER10 Propositions, these issues represent more general and common subjects of a letter, akin to terms found in a 'Schlagwortkatalog' (subject catalogue). In contradistinction to the CER8 Statement Class, which delineates content concerning knowledge transfer, intellectual exchange, and collaborative working processes within the letter texts, the terms enumerated in this class constitute broader thematic aspects of the letters.

Examples:

- Familiennachrichten

- Reise
- Fragmentpoetik

In First Order Logic:

$CER11(x) \Rightarrow E55(x)$

Module “Statement”

In this module, entities are described that express the (sometimes implicit) semantic context of a letter edited by the project team regarding the project’s research questions. The statement’s structure resulting from this annotation process is composed of a subject (CER4 Index Information) – proposition (as predicate) – illocution (as predicate) – object (CER4 Index Information). This annotation aims to query the letter texts for knowledge transfer, intellectual exchange, and collaborative working processes between the correspondence partners. For illocutions and propositions, a controlled vocabulary has been developed by the project which is referenced accordingly. (Suárez Cronauer et al., 2023)

The module “Statement” includes the following classes:

- *CER4 Index Information*
- CER8 Statement
- CER9 Illocution
- CER10 Proposition

CER8 Statement

Subclass of:

E13 Attribute Assignment

Scope Note:

This class comprises semantic statements that are implicitly mentioned within the letters of the early Romanticism period and extracted into a formal syntax by an editor. These statements are defined as 'grundlegende[...] Einheiten einer Erzählung' (Sudhahar et al., 2015) and describe content related to knowledge transfer, intellectual exchange, and collaborative working processes within the letter texts. Although the actual content of these statements is written by a historical person, the implicit and intended meaning, expressed through general terms of a controlled vocabulary, is provided by an editor. It is important to note that modelling such statements involves inherent uncertainty and subjectivity.

The statement class serves as a framing point connected to the classes that make up the contents of the statements. In general, the syntax of these statements can take two forms: either a triple in the form of subject – illocution (as predicate, represented by a verb) – object (SPO-Triple), or a quadruple in the form of subject – illocution (as predicate, represented by a verb) – proposition (as an expanded part of the predicate that describes the range of the verb) – object.

The elements subject and object are represented through the class CER4 Index Information. Within the project context, the subject element is only represented by a person, ergo an instance

of CER4 Index Information connected to an instance of the class CER17 Person. To ensure the flexibility of the model and facilitate later changes to the model, the decision was made to not to set a constraint. The predicate in form of an illocution or a proposition, respectively, is represented through the class CER9 Illocution or CER10 Proposition, respectively.

The instances of this class are represented by statement IDs, which contain information about the triple or quadruple structure of the statement.

Examples:

- Statement-ID 487_1045-22898-23294-766-11 with Subject 'Eschenburg, Johann Joachim', Illocution 'vermitteln lassen', Proposition 'Werk' and Object 'Schlegel, August Wilhelm von'
- Statement-ID 494_766-0000-22954-1402-11 with Subject 'Schlegel, August Wilhelm von ', Illocution 'loben' and Object 'Bürger, Gottfried August'

In First Order Logic:

$CER8(x) \Rightarrow E13(x)$

Properties:

CERP11 implied in (implies): CER3 Lettext

CERP13 has subject (is subject of): CER4 Index Information

CERP14 has object (is object of): CER4 Index Information

CERP15 has illocution (is illocution of): CER9 Illocution

CERP16 has proposition (is proposition of): CER10 Proposition

CER9 Illocution

Subclass of:

E55 Type

Scope Note:

This class comprises the part of the predicate in the form of a verb within the implicit semantic statements mentioned in the letters of the early Romanticism period. In this project, instances of CER9 Illocution are terms from the "Controlled vocabulary for semantic modelling of communication and knowledge transfer in historical letters (c. 1800)" (<https://lod.academy/cer/vocab/terms/>). Its instances consist of verbs related to knowledge transfer, intellectual exchange, and collaborative working processes. The illocutions follow Searle's illocutionary types, which classify verbs into assertive, directive, commissive, expressive, and declarative groups. (Searle, 1976)

Examples:

- <https://lod.academy/cer/vocab/terms#I00057> – mitteilen (inform)
- <https://lod.academy/cer/vocab/terms#I0002> – erbitten (request)
- <https://lod.academy/cer/vocab/terms#I0009> – grüßen (greet)

In First Order Logic:

$CER9(x) \Rightarrow E55(x)$

CER10 Proposition

Subclass of:

E55 Type

Scope Note:

This class comprises the part of the predicate in the form of terms that serve as semantic concepts, describing the scope or range of the verb within the implicit semantic statements mentioned in the letters of the early Romanticism period. In this project, instances of CER10 Proposition are terms from the “Controlled vocabulary for semantic modelling of communication and knowledge transfer in historical letters (c. 1800)” (<https://lod.academy/cer/vocab/terms/>). Its instances consist of terms related to knowledge transfer, intellectual exchange, and collaborative working processes, specifically in connection with research findings in Romanticism studies, letter studies, and the knowledge about the cultural aspects of everyday life during the 1800s.

Examples:

- <https://lod.academy/cer/vocab/terms#P000207> – Kritik (criticism)
- <https://lod.academy/cer/vocab/terms#P000157> – Brief (letter)
- <https://lod.academy/cer/vocab/terms#P000150> – Gesundheit (health)

In First Order Logic:

$CER10(x) \Rightarrow E55(x)$

Module “Biographical Information”

This module contains biographical information which gives further context to instances of the CER17 Person.

At this stage of the project, this concerns the assignment (CER22) of one or more gender attributes (CER23) to historical persons by the project or an external institution (CER7). This modelling of and around gender reflects our view of gender not as a natural or fixed attribute but as a cultural construct and a social mechanism of power. As a historical category that gives insight into power structures and inequalities, it always constitutes an assignment of an attribute by an external actor.

The module “Biographical Information” includes the following classes:

- *CER7 Institution*
- *CER17 Person*
- CER22 Gender Assignment
- CER23 Assigned Gender

CER22 Gender Assignment

Subclass of:

E13 Attribute Assignment

Scope Note:

This class represents the process by which a historical person's gender is assigned through external institutional labeling. The process may involve extracting gender information linked to a person's authority record in the German National Library, or assigning gender via an internal project workflow using the Python library 'gender_guesser' and manual annotation. The assignment of gender is a culturally constructed practice and therefore inherently biased.

Examples:

- The assignment of the gender “female” (CER23) to Caroline von Schelling (CER17) by the Integrated Authority File of the German National Library (GND) (CER7)

In First Order Logic:

CER22(x) ⇒ E13(x)

Properties:

CERP8 carried out by (performed): CER7 Institution

CER17 Person

CERP21 assigned gender attribute to (gender was attributed by): CER17 Person

CERP22 assigned gender property of type (is type of gender property assigned): CER23 Assigned Gender

CER23 Assigned Gender

Subclass of:

E55 Type

Scope Note:

This class comprises the Assigned Gender of a Person (CER17). It does not reflect a (historical) person's self-description of their gender but rather an external labeling through an institution. Gender is therefore defined following Joan W. Scott's definition described in the essay “Gender: A Useful Category of Historical Analysis” (1986), where she describes gender not simply as a synonym for biological sex, but as a primary way of signifying relationships of power. Scott explains that gender operates on two interrelated levels: First, as a constitutive element of social relationships — it organizes social structures, symbols, norms, and identities through the meanings attributed to sexual difference. Second, as a primary field of power — it is a means through which power is articulated, negotiated, and institutionalized in society. Gender is therefore both a cultural construction and a social mechanism of power — not a natural or fixed attribute. It is a historical category that helps explain how societies create and maintain hierarchies and inequalities

Examples:

- female
- male
- unknown

In First Order Logic:

CER23(x) ⇒ E55(x)

Module “Co-Presence”

The module “Co-Presence” includes the following classes:

- *CER2 Reference Data Set (described in Module “Editing”)*
- *CER17 Person*
- *CER18 Time-Span*
- *CER19 Place*
- CER24 Co-Presence
- CER25 Confidence Value

CER24 Co-Presence

Subclass of:

E5 Event

Scope Note:

This class represents the event of co-presence when two historical actors were present at the same time at the same place. This event is inferred from temporal and spatial information given in the letters.

Examples:

- The event of the co-presence of Sophie Bernhardi (CER17) and August Wilhelm Schlegel (CER17) at Berlin (CER19) on 3 January 1802 as inferred from two letters sent by those persons represented by the CER2 Reference Data Sets with the identifiers “AWS-aw-09fo” and “AWS-aw-00xm”

In First Order Logic:

$CER24(x) \Rightarrow E5(x)$

Properties:

CERP6 has time-span (is time-span of): CER18 Time-Span

CERP7 took place at (witnessed): CER19 Place

CERP23 had participant: CER17 Person

CERP24 has confidence value (is confidence value of): CER25 Confidence Value

CER25 Confidence Value

Subclass of:

E55 Type

Scope Note:

This class represents the probability of an assumption derived through reasoning processes in the data, thereby reflecting the uncertainties and ambiguities of inferred events.

While values can be given numerically to be able to compute them, they do not reflect actual probabilities but approximations based on qualitative analysis of the inferred relations. For example, in the reasoning process for co-presence, where a confidence value is assigned to the

inferred relationship, the highest value is 90% to highlight the uncertainties of historical records and of the assumptions built up around them. It is for this reason that the class is modelled as a subclass of E55 Type instead of, for example, E54 Dimension, to highlight the interpretative nature of the value.

Examples:

- The confidence value of 1.8 indicating a high likelihood for the co-presence of Sophie Bernhardt and August Wilhelm Schlegel in Berlin on 3 January 1802 which is calculated from the probabilities of a presence of each respective person in Berlin at this date of 0.9

In First Order Logic:

$CER24(x) \Rightarrow E5(x)$

Module “Editing”

In this module, entities are described that express the editing process of a textual research object, for example a letter’s text, as well as the interdependencies between this process, the researchers, and the research objects. It aims to highlight the editing process as a dynamic and rather subjective structure which is highly dependent on the project’s guidelines and its context, as well as on the person annotating a textual object. By adding this module to the ontology, the traceability and verifiability which led to the editing of a text should be more open and understandable.

The module “Editing” includes the following classes:

- *CER1 Letter*
- CER2 Reference Data Set
- *CER3 Lettertext*
- CER15 Editing
- *CER17 Person*
- *CER18 Time-Span*

CER2 Reference Data Set

Subclass of:

E31Document

Scope Note:

The scope of the ontology covers databases documenting initial transcription and editing of letters but also cases where existing data is gathered and integrated into a secondary database, i.e. a knowledge graph. This class is intended to reference the datasets which are the basis of the secondary database. Therefore, the purpose of this class is to provide a reference for the provenience of the data and to document the editing process of the letters as far as it has happened prior to integration into the current database.

Examples:

- The dataset with the unique identifier “AWS-aw-00lw” in the software FUD² containing the transcribed text of a specific letter and metadata
- The website with the PURL <https://august-wilhelm-schlegel.de/version-01-22/briefid/2564> representing the transcribed, edited, and annotated text and digital image of a letter from Friedrich Ludwig Christian zu Solms-Laubach to August Wilhelm von Schlegel, Friedrich Gottlieb Welcker, Karl Dietrich Hüllmann, and Carl Friedrich Heinrich

In First Order Logic:

$CER2(x) \Rightarrow E73(x)$

Properties:

CERP17 documents (is documented in): CER3 Lettertext

CER1 Letter

CERP20 infers (is inferred from): CER24 Co-Presence

CER15 Editing

Subclass of:

E65 Creation

Scope Note:

This class comprises the various editing events that lead to the creation and development of instances of CER2 Reference Data Set. It provides insights into the editing process, offering a comprehensive overview and, at times, specific details regarding the editing procedure.

Examples:

- Edit_496: with note ‘Entfernung von Fußnotenzeichen’ and status ‘Korrektur der Frakturbriefe’
- ‘dit_487: with note ‘no edit_note’ and status ‘Tripel hinzugefügt’

In First Order Logic:

$CER15(x) \Rightarrow E65(x)$

Properties:

CERP6 has time-span (is time-span of): CER18 Time-Span

CERP8 carried out by (performed): CER17 Person

CERP18 has created (was created by): CER2 Reference Data Set

² For more information about FuD see: <https://fud.uni-trier.de/>

4 CER Ontology Property Declarations

Unlike classes, properties are not organised into modules. Instead, they are listed in numerical order as they often connect different modules or apply to more than one module. The declarations follow the format as established in the definition of the CIDOC CRM.

CERP1 is identified by (identifies)

Domain:

E1 CRM Entity

Range:

CER21 Identifier

Subproperty of:

P1 is identified by (identifies)

Quantification:

one to one, dependent (0,1:1,1)

Scope Note:

This property describes the identification of any item in this knowledge domain by a unique identifier.

Examples:

- August Wilhelm Schlegel (CER17) is identified by the ID “19452” (E41).

In First Order Logic:

$CERP1(x,y) \Rightarrow E1(x)$

$CERP1(x,y) \Rightarrow CER21(y)$

$CERP1(x,y) \Rightarrow P1(x,y)$

CERP2 has language (is language of)

Domain:

CER3 Lettertext

Range:

CER20 Language

Subproperty of:

P72 has language (is language of)

Quantification:

many to many, necessary (1,n:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property describes a specific language in which the text of a letter is written. A text can have one more than language.

Examples:

- The Lettertext (CER3) “Jena d. 7. März 1798. Mein werthester Herr Hofrath, Gestern, da ich erst Abends zurückgekommen war, brachte mir Hr. Horn den ersten Band von der neuen Ausgabe Ihres Shakspeare, welchen Sie die Güte gehabt, ihm für mich mitzugeben. (...)” has language ‘Deutsch’ (CER20).

In First Order Logic:

$CERP2(x,y) \Rightarrow CER3(x)$

$CERP2(x,y) \Rightarrow CER20(y)$

$CERP2(x,y) \Rightarrow P72(x,y)$

CERP3 carries (is carried by)

Domain:

CER1 Letter

Range:

CER3 Lettertext

Subproperty of:

P128 carries (is carried by)

Quantification:

one to many, necessary (1,n:0,1)

Scope Note:

This property defines that an instance of Letter (CER1) as a physical manifestation carries the Lettertext (CER3) as its textual representation. Textual representation for the CER knowledge domain is defined as the content of a letter in its written form. The quantification of this property allows for the possibility that editors identify more than one textual entity in a letter, for example, by identifying and differentiating sections written by different persons.

Examples:

- The Letter (CER1) which was sent between August Wilhelm von Schlegel and Johann Joachim Eschenburg from Jena to Braunschweig on 7 March 1798 carries the lettertext (E33) “Jena d. 7. März 1798. Mein werthester Herr Hofrath, Gestern, da ich erst Abends zurückgekommen war, brachte mir Hr. Horn den ersten Band von der neuen Ausgabe Ihres (...)”.

In First Order Logic:

$CERP3(x,y) \Rightarrow CER1(x)$

$CERP3(x,y) \Rightarrow CER3(y)$

$CERP3(x,y) \Rightarrow P128(x,y)$

CERP4 has generic term (is generic term of)

Domain:

CER3 Lettertext

Range:

CER11 Theme

Subproperty of:

P129 is about (is subject of)

Quantification:

many to many (0,n:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property documents that an instance of a Lettertext (CER3) is about a generic theme (CER11) which describes as a general and common subject the text as a whole, similar to a keyword.

Examples:

- The Lettertext “Monsieur et tres cher Ami! Retournant en ville apres avoir fait un petit voyage dans les provinces et n’ayant rien entendu de votre part (...)” is about “Reise” (CER11).

In First Order Logic:

$CERP4(x,y) \Rightarrow CER3(x)$

$CERP4(x,y) \Rightarrow CER11(y)$

$CERP4(x,y) \Rightarrow P129(x,y)$

CERP5 has component (is component of)

Domain:

CER3 Lettertext

Range:

CER4 Index Information

Subproperty of:

P148 has component (is component of)

Quantification:

many to many (0:n,0:n)

Scope Note:

This property associates an instance of CER3 Lettertext with instances of Index Information (CER4) mentioned within this lettertext. These instances of Index Information (CER4) are by themself a structural part of the Lettertext (CER3) they are mentioned in.

Example:

The Lettertext (CER4) “Monsieur et tres cher Ami! Retournant en ville apres avoir fait un petit voyage dans les provinces et n’ayant rien entendu de votre part (...)” has Index Information (CER4) Groningen, Utrecht, Hamburg, Leipzig, Göttingen, Berlin, Amsterdam, Hannover, Braunschweig, Jena, Caroline von Schelling, Hendrik Muilman, Maria Henriëtte van Castricum, Suzanna Cornelia Hooff, Johannes Jacobus Metelerkamp and Susanna Cornelia Muilman.

In First Order Logic:

$CERP5(x,y) \Rightarrow CER3(x)$
 $CERP5(x,y) \Rightarrow CER4(y)$
 $CERP5(x,y) \Rightarrow P148(x,y)$

CERP6 has time-span (is time-span of)

Domain:

CER12 Correspondence Action
CER15 Editing
CER24 Co-Presence

Range:

CER18 Time-Span

Subproperty of:

P4 has time-span (is time-span of)

Quantification:

many to one, necessary (1,1:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property associates an instance of CER12 Correspondence Action or CER15 Editing or CER24 Co-Presence with one instance of CER18 Time-Span during which the Correspondence Action (CER12) (like Sending (CER13) or Receiving (CER14)) or the Editing process or the inferred Co-Presence of two historical actors was ongoing. The associated instance of CER18 Time-Span is understood as the real time-span during which the phenomena making up the temporal entity instance were active.

Examples:

- The Correspondence Action (CER12) with the ID “send_3774” has time-span “1798-06-15” (CER18).
- The Editing (CER15) with the ID “edit_3774” has time-span 2022-11-04 (CER18).

In First Order Logic:

$CERP6(x,y) \Rightarrow (CER12(x) \vee CER15(x) \vee CER24(x))$
 $CERP6(x,y) \Rightarrow CER18(y)$
 $CERP6(x,y) \Rightarrow P148(x,y)$

CERP7 took place at (witnessed)

Domain:

CER12 Correspondence Action

Range:

CER19 Place

Subproperty of:

P7 took place at (witnessed)

Quantification:

many to many (0,n:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property describes the Place (CER19 Place) where a Correspondence Action (CER12) happened, meaning the sending and receiving place. These places are not known for all letters, making it an optional property.

Examples:

- The Correspondence Action (CER12) with the ID “send_3774” took place at Amsterdam (CER19 Place).

In First Order Logic:

$CERP7(x,y) \Rightarrow CER12(x)$

$CERP7(x,y) \Rightarrow CER19(y)$

$CERP7(x,y) \Rightarrow P7(x,y)$

CERP8 carried out by (performed)

Domain:

CER12 Correspondence Action

CER15 Editing

CER22 Gender Assignment

Range:

CER7 Institution

CER17 Person

Subproperty of:

P14 carried out by (performed)

Quantification:

many to many, necessary (1,n:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property describes the Person (CER17) involved in or responsible for an Editing (Activity) (CER 15) or for a Correspondence Action (CER12), for example sender(s) or receiver(s) of a letter or the Institution (CER7) responsible for a person's Gender Assignment (CER22) in the data.

Examples:

- The Correspondence Action (CER12) with the ID "send_3774" (was) carried out by Willem Ferdinand Mogge Muilman (CER17).
- Jochen Strobel (CER17) performed Editing (CER15) with the ID "edit_3774".

In First Order Logic:

$CERP8(x,y) \Rightarrow (CER12(x) \vee CER15(x) \vee CER22(x))$

$CERP8(x,y) \Rightarrow (CER7(y) \vee CER17(y))$

$CERP8(x,y) \Rightarrow P14(x,y)$

CERP9 was intended use of (was made for)

Domain:

CER12 Correspondence Action

Range:

CER1 Letter

Subproperty of:

P19 was intended use of (was made for)

Quantification:

many to one, necessary (1,1:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property relates an instance of CER12 Correspondence Action with instances of CER1 Letter, which was created specifically for this Correspondence Action. This means that the intended use of a letter in the knowledge domain of the CER-ontology is that it's part of a Correspondence Action. The Correspondence Action (in Sending or Receiving) is the crucial difference between a text as a document or composition and a text as a letter in terms of a communication medium. However, information on senders and receivers is not known for all letters, making it an optional property for its range.

Examples:

- The Letter with the ID "ref_3774" (CER1) was made for (or was written for) the Correspondence Action (CER12) with the ID "send_3774".

In First Order Logic:

$CERP9(x,y) \Rightarrow CER12(x)$

$CERP9(x,y) \Rightarrow CER1(y)$

$CERP9(x,y) \Rightarrow P19(x,y)$

CERP10 lists (is listed in)

Domain:

CER16 Authority Record

Range:

CER4 Index Information

Subproperty of:

P71 lists (is listed in)

Quantification:

one to one (1,1:0,1)

Scope Note:

This property associates an instance of CER16 Authority Record, with an instance of CER4 Index Information (e.g. mentioned persons, places, periodicals, works and/or institutions) which it lists for reference purposes.

Examples:

- The GND-entry <https://d-nb.info/gnd/118607049> (CER16) lists Caroline von Schlegel as mentioned in a letter (CER4).

In First Order Logic:

$CERP10(x,y) \Rightarrow CER16(x)$

$CERP10(x,y) \Rightarrow CER4(y)$

$CERP10(x,y) \Rightarrow P71(x,y)$

CERP11 implied in (implies)

Domain:

CER8 Statement

Range:

CER3 Lettertext

Subproperty of:

P17 was motivated by (motivated)

Quantification:

many to one, necessary (1,1:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property describes the appearance of one or more statements within the text of a letter. It connects a statement with the lettertext in which this statement is mentioned implicitly.

Examples:

- The Statement (CER8) with the ID 487_1045-22898-23294-766-11 and with Subject 'Eschenburg, Johann Joachim', Illocution 'vermitteln lassen', Proposition 'Werk' and Object 'Schlegel, August Wilhelm von' (CER8) refers to the Lettext (CER3) "Jena d. 7. März 1798. Mein werthester Herr Hofrath, Gestern, da ich erst Abends zurückgekommen war, brachte mir Hr. Horn den ersten Band von der neuen Ausgabe Ihres Shakspeare, welchen Sie die Güte gehabt, ihm für mich mitzugeben. (...)".

In First Order Logic:

$CERP11(x,y) \Rightarrow CER8(x)$

$CERP11(x,y) \Rightarrow CER3(y)$

$CERP11(x,y) \Rightarrow P17(x,y)$

CERP12 is about (is subject of)

Domain:

CER4 Index Information

Range:

CER5 Periodical

CER6 Work

CER7 Institution

CER17 Person

CER19 Place

Subproperty of:

P129 is about (is subject of)

Quantification:

many to one, necessary (1,1:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property documents that an instance of the Index Information (CER4) within lettertext is about a specific thing in the real world like a Person (CER17), Institution (CER7), Work (CER6), Periodical (CER5) or Place (CER19). The instance of the Index Information (CER4) represents the textual abstraction of these things in the context of a letter. Nevertheless these things exist as realities in the real world independently of the letter or its context.

Examples:

- The Index Information (CER4) "Schelling, Caroline von" is about the Person "Caroline von Schelling" (CER17).
- The Index Information (CER4) "Vater", as contained in the text (CER3) of a letter (CER1) by Karl August Schlegel, is about the Person "Johann Adolf Schlegel" (CER17).

In First Order Logic:

$CERP12(x,y) \Rightarrow CER4(x)$

$CERP12(x,y) \Rightarrow (CER5(y) \vee CER6(y) \vee CER7(y) \vee CER17(y) \vee CER19(y))$

$CERP12(x,y) \Rightarrow P129(x,y)$

CERP13 has subject (is subject of)

Domain:

CER8 Statement

Range:

CER4 Index Information

Subproperty of:

P140 assigned attribute to (was attributed by)

Quantification:

many to one, necessary (1,1:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property associates an instance of CER8 Statement with an instance of CER4 Index Information in the role of subject of this statement. For the knowledge domain in the CER-ontology, only Index Information which is about a Person (CER17) can be attributed as subjects. This is expressed through restrictions in the logical data model, but on a conceptual level all entities in a letter can potentially be assigned as subjects of a statement.

Examples:

- The statement with the ID 487_766-22941-23059-1045-11 (CER8 Statement) *has_Subject* Schlegel, August Wilhelm von (CER17 Person)
- The statement with the ID 487_1045-0000-23294-6167-12 (CER8 Statement) *has_Subject* Eschenburg, Johann Joachim (CER17 Person)

In First Order Logic:

$CERP13(x,y) \Rightarrow CER8(x)$

$CERP13(x,y) \Rightarrow CER4(y)$

$CERP13(x,y) \Rightarrow P140(x,y)$

CERP14 has object (is object of)

Domain:

CER8 Statement

Range:

CER4 Index Information

Subproperty of:

P141 assigned (was assigned by)

Quantification:

many to one, necessary (1,1:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property associates an instance of CER8 Statement with the instance of CER4 Index Information used in the attribution. As a result, the instance of CER4 Index Information becomes the object of this statement.

Examples:

- The statement with the ID 487_766-22941-23059-1045-11 (CER8 Statement) *has_Object* Eschenburg, Johann Joachim (CER4 Index Information)
- The statement with the ID 487_1045-0000-23294-6167-12 (CER8 Statement) *has_Object* Shakespeare, William: Schauspiele [Ü: Johann Joachim Eschenburg] (CER4 Index Information)

In First Order Logic:

$CERP14(x,y) \Rightarrow CER8(x)$
 $CERP14(x,y) \Rightarrow CER4(y)$
 $CERP14(x,y) \Rightarrow P141(x,y)$

CERP15 has illocution (is illocution of)

Domain:

CE8 Statement

Range:

CE9 Illocution

Subproperty of:

P177 assigned property of type (is type of property assigned)

Quantification:

many to one, necessary (1,1:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property associates an instance of CER8 Statement with an instance of CER9 Illocution, which has the role of the verb or predicate in this statement. It constitutes the connection between the subject and the object of a statement and is mandatory.

Examples:

- The statement with the ID 487_766-22941-23059-1045-11 (CE8 Statement) *has_Illocution* ankündigen (CER9 Illocution)
- The statement with the ID 487_1045-0000-23294-6167-12 (CE8 Statement) *has_Illocution* vermitteln lassen (CER9 Illocution)

In First Order Logic:

$CERP15(x,y) \Rightarrow CER8(x)$
 $CERP15(x,y) \Rightarrow CER9(y)$
 $CERP15(x,y) \Rightarrow P177(x,y)$

CERP16 has proposition (is proposition of)

Domain:

CER8 Statement

Range:

CER10 Proposition

Subproperty of:

P177 assigned property of type (is type of property assigned)

Quantification:

many to one (0,1:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property associates an instance of CER8 Statement with an instance of CER10 Proposition, which serves as an expansion that specifies the range of the verb or predicate in a statement. It gives more context to the illocution of a statement and is optional.

Examples:

- The statement with the ID 487_766-22941-23059-1045-11 (CER8 Statement) *has Proposition* Buchsendung (CE10 Proposition)
- The statement with the ID 487_1045-22898-23294-766-11 (CER8 Statement) *has Proposition* Werk (CE10 Proposition)

In First Order Logic:

$CERP16(x,y) \Rightarrow CER8(x)$

$CERP16(x,y) \Rightarrow CER10(y)$

$CERP16(x,y) \Rightarrow P177(x,y)$

CERP17 documents (is documented in)

Domain:

CER2 Reference Data Set

Range:

CER1 Letter

CER3 Lettext

Subproperty of:

P70 documents (is documented in)

Quantification:

many to many, necessary (1,n:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property describes the connection between an instance of a CER2 Reference Data Set that documents an instance of CER3 Lettertext or CER1 Letter. This property intent is to show that this Reference Data Set (CER2) isn't representing the content of a letter as a whole but only the parts of a letter (in this case the lettertext). Both lettertext and letter are the result of an editing process. Even though the original manuscript existed in the real world, an instance of Letter (CER1) embodies its representation in scholarly editions, as digital copies and inferred letters. These representations are then collected in an editing software, which is the database for instances of CER1 Letter. The Lettertext (CER3) which is referred to is already an edited text in terms of a research object, which is making a proposition about reality.

Examples:

- The Reference Data Set (CER2) in the editing software FUD with the key "AWS-aw-02in" documents the Lettertext (CER3) "Monsieur et tres cher Ami! Retournant en ville apres avoir fait un petit voyage dans les provinces et n'ayant rien entendu de votre part (...)"
- The Reference Data Set (CER2) in the editing software FUD with the key "AWS-aw-02in" documents the Letter (CER1) which is archived in the Saxon State and University Library in Dresden under the signature "Mscr.Dresd.e.90, XIX, Bd.15, Nr.91".

In First Order Logic:

$CERP17(x,y) \Rightarrow CER2(x)$
 $CERP17(x,y) \Rightarrow (CER1(y) \vee CER3(y))$
 $CERP17(x,y) \Rightarrow P70(x,y)$

CERP18 has created (was created by)

Domain:

CER15 Editing

Range:

CER2 Reference Data Set

Subproperty of:

P94 has created (was created by)

Quantification:

many to one, necessary, dependent (1,1:1,n)

Scope Note:

This property links an instance of CER15 Editing to the instance of CER2 Reference Data Set, which was created in an editing process. Thereby it represents the research process of conceptualising the intellectual content of the instance of CER2 Reference Data Set. It does not necessarily represent the act of creating the first digital carrier of the instance of CER2 Reference Data Set, but rather the process that concludes to the data set which represents the sources (the lettertexts) in the project "Correspondence of Early Romanticism".

Examples:

- The Editing (CER15) with the string of “Erste Transkription” (CER21) has created the Reference Data Set with the key “AWS-aw-02in” (CER2) in the editing software FUD.

In First Order Logic:

$CERP18(x,y) \Rightarrow CER15(x)$

$CERP18(x,y) \Rightarrow CER2(y)$

$CERP18(x,y) \Rightarrow P94(x,y)$

CERP19 had duration (was duration of)

Domain:

CER18 Time-Span

Range:

CER26 Start Date

CER27 End Date

Subproperty of:

P191 had duration (was duration of)

Quantification:

one to many, necessary, dependent (1,n:1,1)

Scope Note:

This property links an instance of CER18 Time-Span to an instance of either CER26 Start-Date or CER27 End-Date, representing the beginning and end points of the time-span.

Examples:

- The Time Span “1.–3. Mai 1787” has the duration “1787-05-01” (CER26) to “1787-05-03” (CER27)

In First Order Logic:

$CERP19(x,y) \Rightarrow CER18(x)$

$CERP19(x,y) \Rightarrow (CER26(y) \vee CER27(y))$

$CERP19(x,y) \Rightarrow P191(x,y)$

CERP20 infers (is inferred from)

Domain:

CER2 Reference Data Set

Range:

CER24 Co-Presence

Subproperty of:

CERP17 documents

Quantification:

many to many, dependent (0,n:1,n)

Scope Note:

This property links an instance of CER2 Reference Data Set to an instance of CER24 Co-Presence. The interpretation of two CER2 Reference Data Sets provides the basis for the assumption or inference that a co-presence between two historical actors occurred, thereby giving rise to this assertion.

Examples:

- Two letters sent by Sophie Bernhardt and August Wilhelm Schlegel with the identifiers “AWS-aw-09fo” and “AWS-aw-00xm” (CER2 Reference Data Set) infer the co-presence (CER24) of those persons in Berlin on 3 January 1802.

In First Order Logic:

$CERP20(x,y) \Rightarrow CER2(x)$

$CERP20(x,y) \Rightarrow CER24(y)$

$CERP20(x,y) \Rightarrow CERP17(x,y)$

CERP21 assigned gender attribute to (gender was attributed by)

Domain:

CER22 Gender Assignment

Range:

CER17 Person

Subproperty of:

P140 assigned attribute to (was attributed by)

Quantification:

many to one, necessary (1,1:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property links a Gender Assignment (CER22) to a Person (CER17), indicating the assigned gender value (female, male, or unknown). This assignment does not necessarily reflect the gender a historical person would use to describe themselves, but rather the interpretation of the institution responsible for the assignment.

Examples:

- The GND (CER7) conducted a gender assignment (CER22) in which it assigned a gender to Caroline von Schelling (CER17).

In First Order Logic:

$CERP21(x,y) \Rightarrow CER22(x)$

$CERP21(x,y) \Rightarrow CER17(y)$

$CERP21(x,y) \Rightarrow P140(x,y)$

CERP22 assigned gender property of type (is type of gender property assigned)

Domain:

CER22 Gender Assignment

Range:

CER23 Assigned Gender

Subproperty of:

P177 assigned property of type (is type of property assigned)

Quantification:

many to many, necessary (1,n:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property links an instance of CER22 Gender Assignment to an instance of CER23 Assigned Gender, thereby connecting the process of assigning a person's gender with the resulting gender type.

Examples:

- The GND (CER7) conducted a gender assignment (CER22) in which it assigned a gender property of the type "female" (CER23)

In First Order Logic:

$CERP22(x,y) \Rightarrow CER22(x)$

$CERP22(x,y) \Rightarrow CER23(y)$

$CERP22(x,y) \Rightarrow P177(x,y)$

CERP23 had participant (participated in)

Domain:

CER24 Co-Presence

Range:

CER17 Person

Subproperty of:

P11 had participant (participated in)

Quantification:

many to many, necessary (1,n:0,n)

Scope Note:

This property describes the participation of at least two instances of the class CER17 Person to an inferred Co-Presence (CER24).

Examples:

- Sophie Bernhardi (CER17) and August Wilhelm Schlegel (CER17) participated in an event of Co-Presence (CER24) in Berlin on 1 March 1802.

In First Order Logic:

$CERP23(x,y) \Rightarrow CER24(x)$

$CERP23(x,y) \Rightarrow CER17(y)$

$CERP23(x,y) \Rightarrow P11(x,y)$

CERP24 has confidence value (is confidence value of)

Domain:

CER24 Co-Presence

Range:

CER25 Confidence Value

Subproperty of:

P2 has type (is type of)

Quantification:

one to one (1,1:1,1)

Scope Note:

This property assigns a confidence value to an event inferred in a reasoning process which describes the probability of this event having taken place. As, at this point in time, the CIDOC CRM does not allow the connection of measurements or other value attributes to events, this property is modelled as a subproperty of P2 has type (is type of).

Examples:

- The co-presence of Sophie Bernhardi and August Wilhelm Schlegel in Berlin on 3 January 1802 has a confidence value of 1.8, calculated from the probabilities of a presence of each respective person in Berlin at this date of 0.9.

In First Order Logic:

$CERP24(x,y) \Rightarrow CER24(x)$

$CERP24(x,y) \Rightarrow CER25(y)$

$CERP24(x,y) \Rightarrow P2(x,y)$

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